

USING AUTHENTIC MATERIALS ON ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract: The article discusses the problems of using authentic materials on teaching foreign languages. Using authentic materials in the class can be a useful tool to motivate pupils and make them feel comfortable using the foreign language. Authentic materials, if used properly in authentic learning environments, can have lots of uses in foreign language teaching though they are not specifically designed to teach a foreign language. For this reason, foreign language teachers should act as a guide for the students to interact with the authentic materials in constructivist learning environments. In addition, learning environments in which authentic materials are used should be organized when training prospective foreign language teachers to set an example for the teachers of the future to use authentic materials in their own classrooms. In that way, prospective teachers will have a chance to see and experience, themselves, the advantages of these materials and points to consider when using them. The aim of the present study is to focus on the importance and the uses of authentic materials in foreign language teacher training program and to come up with some suggestions concerning the matter.

Keywords: communication, foreign languages, skills, authentic materials.

Language is a tool of communication which connects people. They send and receive messages through communication. There are 6500 living languages in the world, which attract people to learn foreign languages. Learning a foreign language is made linguists to work out in the sphere of philology to create an effective way for gaining knowledge. English is a very productive language. English is the fourth most widely spoken native language in the world, and in terms of sheer number of speakers, it is the most spoken official language in the world. It is the primary language used in international affairs[1]. The role of foreign languages in modern society has made educators devise new ways of teaching them so that their results match the learners' needs and expectations. Acquiring a foreign language implies developing several skills in the target language which sometimes can be a challenge for pupils, especially when they are exposed to real-life situations of communication.

As the present generation of learners gets the opportunity of using numerous sources to learn any subject, the use of authentic materials seems to be a great help for them to improve their learning skills. The teachers can use the authentic material as additional material to develop the overall skills of the learners' learning. With the help of the authentic material, the teachers can reinforce the learning items and can

give additional tasks to the learners[2]. Furthermore, these authentic materials create interest among the learners since the teachers select them with proper care by taking the needs and interests of the learners. As a result, the learners can participate with more enthusiasm in the given tasks and try to perform the tasks with utmost care and concentration. Authentic materials are abundantly used in the teaching of English by the teachers to attain better results while teaching the learners in the English language classrooms.

Since the authentic materials are more economic and effortlessly available anywhere and anytime, the teachers of English can use them to teach in their regular ELT classrooms. There are many authentic materials available to teach English such as News Papers, Brochures, Pamphlets, Flyers, Advertisements, Greeting Cards, Invitation Cards, Post-Cards, Wall Papers, Comics, Cartoons, Story Books, Agony Columns, Directories, Maps, Magazines, Journals, Pictures, Audio Cassettes, Images, TV Programmes, TV Ads, Movies, Songs, Internet Notices, Bus or Train Timetables, Recipe, Menus, Stamps, Tickets, Product Labels, Realia such as phones and dolls, Currency, Weather Reports, Puppets and so on[4].

Magazines are enormously used as rich source of authentic materials in the ELT classrooms as they are very motivating and inspire a wide range of activities. Magazines help the learners in developing the language skills, vocabulary and grammar[6]. Magazines contain a substantial quantity of information and a wide variety of text types.

Brochures, pamphlets and flyers are the best key tools used for language teaching to promote the learners language skills and all of them are used for advertisement that offer a great and real information for the learners. In fact brochures are cost effective and they are widely used in teaching and learning English. Brochures come in numerous shapes and sizes and often come in bi-fold or tri-fold layout used as flyers, coupons or business cards. The teachers can encourage the learners to gather various brochures of museums, banks, libraries, travel agencies, car rental agencies and so on. Then the teachers can select any brochure where the hours of business are clearly visible. By using these brochures, the teachers can introduce several role-plays with the students according to their interests. This also paves a way to review the days of the week also. The teachers can also present their learners with a wide variety of travel brochures and involve the learners to talk about each of the destinations. The teachers should give a chance to the learners to select a particular destination and ask them to write about it why they like to travel to that particular place. Using the travel brochure, the teachers can enhance the language skills of the learners. The teachers can also ask the learners to collect some medical brochures from doctors' offices and use them to have some

dialogue practices[7]. Once the learners read the brochures in detail, the teachers can give them some comprehension questions to answer.

In this paper, an attempt has been made to focus on the effective use of the authentic materials by the teachers in English language classrooms. First, this paper has discussed the advantages of authentic material in education. After that, this paper has brought out the importance of the authentic materials in the English language classrooms. Furthermore, this paper has emphasized mainly on the effective use of the authentic materials and how they are useful the teachers in their teaching and also how they help the learners to learn the English language in an easy and different way. Finally, this paper has also given some expedient hints not only to the teachers of English but also the learners to develop their teaching and learning skills colossally using the authentic materials in the English classrooms

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